

Online Journal on Mobility Cultures and Policies

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	Issue 1 (March 2021)	3
1.2	Issue 2 (July 2021)	4
1.3	Issue 3 (November 2021)	5
1.4	Issue 4 (March 2022)	6
1.5	Issue 5 (July 2022)	7
1.6	Issue 6 (November 2022)	8
2	Conclusions	10

1 INTRODUCTION

REBALANCE published an Online Journal on Mobility Cultures and Policies for Europe in the 21st century every four months (6 in total). The first issue was devoted to introduce the project and the visions of the thinkers, exploring cultures and policies in the Covid19 aftermath, and the last one to introduce the Cultural & Political Manifesto: Making Mobility Meaningful to People. All the major dissemination events were published in the Rebalance Journal.

All the Journal Issues were disseminated via Rebalance Newsletter and Social Networks.

1.1 Issue 1 (March 2021)

Figure Issue 1. Screenshot

1.2 Issue 2 (July 2021)

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ISSUE 1 | ISSUE 2 | ISSUE 3 | ISSUE 4 | ISSUE 5 | ISSUE 6

Journal of Mobility Cultures & Policies

Ideas for a New Mobility Paradigm

ISSUE 2 | JULY 2021

REBALANCE

NEW MOBILITY CULTURES & POLICIES

REBALANCE is proud to present its second edition of the Journal of Mobility Cultures & Policies. As part of the REBALANCE initiative, ten interviews were conducted investigating the effects of the pandemic on mobility, values that underlie our mobility cultures, historically and at present, limitations within the modeling, planning and execution of mobility policy, and visions for the future. Just as mobility is a field which encompasses many different facets of society, the experts interviewed also represent this multiplicity.

Read more

Co-Creating a Manifesto

Co-creative development of a Manifesto for a new European mobility culture and policy.

REBALANCE welcomes participation from the public and exists as a platform where multidisciplinary ideas and people from all over the world can converge, meet, challenge, and eventually transform what we know as mobility today.

Participate

Explorative Conversations

In the coming weeks, we will continue our discussions about mobility cultures and visions for the future. Topics as automated cars, the prospect of a car-less future, digitalization, green transportation, and the patterns of life, work and shopping throughout Europe and in the modern urban world. With newfound insight on the values that impact the choices we make and policies we vote for, we will focus on how to consider the above topics with corresponding values in mind.

More Info

- CALL FOR IDEAS -
Still Open

We invite master students, doctoral candidates, postdoc researchers, early career investigators and university teachers from different disciplinary backgrounds to report on ongoing research, experiences, challenges and opportunities for a mobility paradigm shift after the Covid-19.

More Info

In this paper, Moïse encourages the use of the e-scooter in urban settings claiming it has the power to be very important connective tissue and fill certain gaps where public transportation is more sparse and in need of a "micromobile," solution.

Towards an urban system embracing small, micro, and collective, macro modes?
By: Dylan Moïse

Figure Issue 2. Screenshot

1.3 Issue 3 (November 2021)

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ISSUE 1 | ISSUE 2 | ISSUE 3 | ISSUE 4 | ISSUE 5 | ISSUE 6

Journal of Mobility Cultures & Policies

Ideas for a New Mobility Paradigm

ISSUE 3 | NOVEMBER 2021

The Role of Communication in Shaping the European Mobility Culture

- NEW TALKS -

As part of the REBALANCE initiative, talks will continue once a month in dialogue with Andreu Ullied.

Dec. 16th, 2021
Mark Coeckelbergh, Professor of Philosophy of Media and Tech at the Univ. of Vienna, *collaborating an ethical impact assessment of research and innovation*

Jan. 27th, 2022
Noel B. Salazar, sociocultural anthropologist known for his transdisciplinary work on mobility and travel.

Feb. 24th, 2022
Marta C. González, Expert in computer model developments that analyse digital traces of information mediated by devices, Univ. of California, Berkeley

Mar. 31st, 2022
Massimo Moraglio, coordinator of the MBA Sustainable Mobility at the Berlin Tech Univ., working on tech and its wide effects on economic, social and cultural fields.

[Register](#)

REBALANCE aims at describing the narrative and the essences that shape the mobility culture of today.

Issue 3 will help visualize the influence, over time, of communication on the European mobility culture and how the media have conveyed and represented mobility concepts. Cultural changes can be analysed, among other things, through the evolution of the mainstream language used by media and the way values are channelled to citizens: advertisements, movies, press articles, artistic production, video games, social media, etc. Word- and image-search is performed to this end on a significant sample of popular communication, spanning several decades, in order to unveil signals and messages reflecting the evolution of the mainstream mobility culture and to identify dominant representations of explicit or underlying values and their dynamics over time.

Cultural practices both reflect and define group identities, whether the group is a small subculture or a nation. Thus, the cultural field is the place for creativity and meaning making. But it is also a battlefield: who controls the media and popular culture and what messages they communicate are central to how social life is organized and how power operates.

The media are arguably the most important form of cultural production in our society. Digital technologies are creating new ways of participating in the media that are changing the very foundations of cultural production and consumption.

overemphasis on speed and comfort optimization for traffic and instead show a growing environmental and health consciousness, intensive use of digital technologies, and a tendency towards sharing instead of owning. Will they initiate the cultural shift that will allow us to achieve a sustainable mobility culture?

The Beginnings of Contemporary Transport and Mobility

From Modernity until Yesterday

Today and the Near Future

Generative Dialogues on Theoretical Framework

Dialogues with high-level mobility experts to validate the mobility cultures and values that need to shift from the economic model of the rational decision maker, looking into the fundamentals of the mobility culture of today.

Laetitia Dablanc, Christoph Walther, Luca Bertolini, Bernhard Schlag, Chris Nash, Robert Cervero, Udo Becker, Farideh Ramjerdi, Ralf Risser

Figure Issue 3. Screenshot

1.4 Issue 4 (March 2022)

[About](#) | [Talks](#) | [Conversations](#) | [Journal](#) | [Manifesto](#) | [Insights](#) | [Library](#)

[ISSUE 1](#) | [ISSUE 2](#) | [ISSUE 3](#) | [ISSUE 4](#) | [ISSUE 5](#) | [ISSUE 6](#)

Journal of Mobility Cultures & Policies

Ideas for a New Mobility Paradigm

ISSUE 4 | MARCH 2022

Explorative Conversations: Gaining Insights into Future Mobility Issues

This explorative conversation series is a curated compilation of REBALANCE's dialogues centered on mobility future. Dialogues 1 and 2 speak about technological innovation: here we focus on automated vehicles and the relevance of freedom and control, as well as highlighting the importance of inclusion before digitalization, and when we do digitalize, it is a mean and sustainability is the goal. Dialogues 3 and 4 touch on the future: in these sections, we question the effectiveness of a green mobility transition without an accompanying attitude shift and the importance of convincing people that their real need lies within the agency over movement. Lastly, Dialogue 5 emphasizes the significance for technology in all sectors to be steered because technology isn't inherently fair – however, by prioritizing awareness and inclusion we have a better chance of changing assumptions and our future for the better.

"Freedom and control are two major concepts that come into play when considering people's reliance on automation."
Ghadir Pourhashem & Cristina Pronello

"Trust is a key for adopting new technologies, considering digitalisation as a mean and sustainability as a goal."
Benjamin Doboquir & Xavier Tackoen

"How effective would a green mobility transition be without a major shift in the attitude of citizens and mobility users?"
Robert Braun & Andreu Ulled

"A radical shift to shared schemes could not be enough to curb the dramatic impacts of automobility."
Jens Schade & Stefan Gossling

"Cities should be balanced between density and green spaces."
Alain L'Hostis & Cristina Marolda

Check Rebalance latest Talks ...

"Multi-scalar mobilities is central to understanding the complexities of the current global condition".
Noel B. Salazar

- NEW TALKS -

As part of the REBALANCE initiative, talks will continue once a month in dialogue with Andreu Ulled.

April 28th, 2022

Mónica Bernabé, Spanish journalist known for her work as a correspondent in Ukraine and Afghanistan. In her Talk we will address central and mobility, from mobility as a fundamental right to gender issues.

May 26th, 2022

Daniel Inerarity, Philosopher, professor of political and social philosophy at the Univ. of the Basque Country and director of the Democratic Governance Institute. He is currently Directeur d'Études Associé de la Maison des Sciences de l'Homme (Paris).

[Register](#)

Reinventing Cost-Benefit Analysis for Sustainable Multimodal Mobility

Initial assumption that the culture of mobility, which currently prevails in Europe has led to unsustainable patterns, in social and environmental terms, a critical review of the evolution, the objectives and goals of the transport and mobility policies in Europe has been carried out. This has allowed to identify that the development of sustainable multimodal mobility as one of the key challenges for European cities and functional urban areas.

[Read Article](#)

Figure Issue 4. Screenshot

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the grant agreement No. 101007019

6

1.5 Issue 5 (July 2022)

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ISSUE 1 | ISSUE 2 | ISSUE 3 | ISSUE 4 | ISSUE 5 | ISSUE 6

Journal of Mobility Cultures & Policies

Ideas for a New Mobility Paradigm
ISSUE 5 | JULY 2022

Visions for the Future of Mobility: The Scenario Building Process

REBALANCE moves from the assumption that the mobility culture that currently prevails in the world (including Europe) has led to unsustainable travel patterns, in social and environmental terms. From a critical review of the present also in the light of the recent COVID pandemic, REBALANCE is building a vision over the future and a roadmap to achieve it, which will be embedded in a Manifesto with the aim to stimulate European policymakers to adapt concrete legal and political measures while moving the wider European communities towards a radical change.

A variety of foresight studies have been carried out in recent years to explore the future dynamics of transport and mobility. Many of these projects focus primarily on the future of technologies, or on specific transport sectors.

The original focus of REBALANCE entails a novel and deeper attention to the cultural and value-based factors that play a role in collective and individual mobility choices and orientations, notably including modal choices and travel behaviours on the demand side, and the planning of infrastructure and innovative services on the supply side.

Issue 5 will guide you through the scenario building process we have undertaken during the last months, which in line with the mainstream foresight methodologies – starts with horizon scanning and ends with the narratives of the REBALANCE scenarios and a vision for the mobility future.

Trends & Drivers

Alternative Narratives

The Vision

- REBALANCE LATEST TALKS -

"Technology is always partially human"
Mark Coekebergh

central to understand the complexities of the current global condition"
Noel Salazar

"Human patterns and nowcasting: Science and technology at the service of social well-being"
Marta González

"Beyond empowerment: The growing relevance of mobility's dark-side"
Massimo Moraglio

[Check more](#)

rebalance talks

"The Beauty of Sustainable Mobility: Embedding the New Bauhaus Vision in our Future Mobility Paradigm".
Filippo Fimiani

Figure Issue 5. Screenshot

1.6 Issue 6 (November 2022)

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ISSUE 1 | ISSUE 2 | ISSUE 3 | ISSUE 4 | ISSUE 5 | ISSUE 6

Journal of Mobility Cultures & Policies

Ideas for a New Mobility Paradigm

ISSUE 6 | NOVEMBER 2022

Making Mobility Meaningful to People

CULTURAL AND POLITICAL MANIFESTO

After two years of intensive high-level discussions and deliberations across Europe on all the fundamentals of transport policy embedded in the current mobility paradigm, we are pleased to present to you the **Rebalance Cultural and Political Manifesto**. It is the result of the critical review of the present, the vision for the future and the roadmap to achieve it, with the aim of stimulating European politicians to adopt concrete legal and political measures while moving the wider European communities towards a change radical. We invite you to listen to some of the responses we have already received and to read and sign the Final Manifesto if you agree with it.

[Download the Manifesto](#)

"As the Manifesto states very clearly, at the heart of the problem is that we live in a culture of optimization. This particular philosophy of time, it seems to me, views time as a resource that must be measured and mastered somehow. According to an accountant view of time, the time optimization is how we should value time, and I think this is newly questioned, and rebalance is precisely trying to address this".

Judy Wajcman, Sociologist and expert in the field of science and technology

"I love the fact that the subtitle of the Manifesto has the word meaningful in it. Because for me, the core of the solid philosophy is reconnecting us with meaning. Not doing, not ticking boxes, but meaning, purpose, that all those deeper things that can never be accelerated, you can never speed up meaning. You can't download meaning from Amazon or find it in an app. Meaning only blossoms, flourishes, becomes real when we slow down, when we are present, when we give it the time it deserves, and, of course, when we bring meaning to the journey itself".

Carl Honoré, Best selling author and voice of the global slow movement

CULTURAL AND POLITICAL MANIFESTO: Making Mobility Meaningful to People

OUR CLAIM: A RADICAL CULTURAL CHANGE IN MOBILITY IS ON ITS WAY!

- A cultural change in mobility is already happening
- The relationship between modernity and mobility is double-edged
- We still live in a culture of optimizing time
- Technology may produce place detachment and time alienation
- Disruptive technologies subverts the first law of geography
- We are entering a time of more radical dychronicity

+ Technological development seduces us into thinking that technology will perform better than humans

OUR VISION: A WORLD FREE FROM MEANINGLESS MOBILITY

- + We advocate a rebalancing of mobility
- + We propose care as a core value in transport policies
- + We believe that mobility should always be meaningful, not forced and compulsory
- + We agree with the new Mobility Paradigm
- + We support the Slow Movement

OUR POLITICAL PROPOSAL: MAKING MOBILITY MEANINGFUL TO PEOPLE

- + We propose to go beyond the notion of useful and sustainable transport services
- + We argue that seamless transport should not be our paramount goal
- + We support land-use and time-sensitive policies
- + We welcome a promotion of more Active Mobility
- + We stand for Mobility Justice: mobility impacts on groups, classes and sectors differently

- + We encourage policies that aim to shift from the current approach based on making traffic flows more efficient
- + We welcome the widespread adoption of Urban Sustainable Mobility Plans that improve the city as a whole
- + We support the -Vision Zero- policy that aims to eliminate road fatalities and injuries to almost zero
- + We know that policies aiming to rebalance mobility may fail

[→ Sign the Manifesto](#)

Listen to Andreu Ulled's introduction to the Manifesto

Listen to Carl Honoré responding to the Manifesto

Listen to Judy Wajcman responding to the Manifesto

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Figure Issue 6. Screenshot

2 CONCLUSIONS

The Rebalance online Online Journal on Mobility Cultures and Policies served as a channel for the dissemination of the project and the multiple deliberative events that took place, from the beginning of the project to its end (November 2022). These Journals will remain as a repository for the content generated by the project, including the numerous interviews with experts and the most interesting publications for the community of those interested in a paradigm shift in including Rebalance Cultural and Political Manifesto: Making Mobility Meaningful to People.

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